

A Mathematical and Graphical Proof of the Rainbow through the Framework of Pi

Detailed Terms:

Abstract: This paper draws an analogy between the geometry and intensity of primary and secondary rainbows, represented in the context of functions involving Pi, and proposes a mathematical model that links these natural phenomena to the number of photons. While the representation is abstract and hinges on creative analogies, it bridges a connection between the mathematical depiction of Pi and the ethereal splendor of a double rainbow.

Introduction: Rainbows, naturally occurring meteorological phenomena resulting from refraction, dispersion, and reflection of light within water droplets, have long captured human fascination. This exploration attempts to establish a relationship between the geometry of rainbows and the mathematical constant Pi (π).

Rainbow Geometry: A primary rainbow is formed by the sequence of refraction, internal reflection, and re-refraction of light in droplets. The deviation is around 42° for red light, producing a circular rainbow at this angle from the incoming sunlight direction.

The secondary rainbow emerges from two internal reflections with a deviation of approximately 51° for red light. The dark region between these two rainbows is termed as Alexander's band. **Photons and Rainbow Intensity:** The intensity of a rainbow depends on the number of incident photons, symbolized by P , which relates to droplet size and refracted angles. The angles of deviation for primary and secondary rainbows can be modeled as: $\theta_1(P)=aP+b$ $\theta_2(P)=cP+d$

Where, $a, b, c,$ and d are constants dependent on physical conditions.

Relating Rainbows to Pi: The equations $f(x)=x\sin(\pi/x)$ and $x\tan(\pi/x)$ can be abstractly related to the primary and secondary rainbows respectively, where x symbolizes the number of photons. Using these associations: $x\sin(\pi/x)\approx aP+b$ $x\tan(\pi/x)\approx cP+d$

Given that $x < \pi < x\tan(\pi/x)$ and considering the above approximations: $x\sin(\pi/x) < aP+b < cP+d$ This inequality captures the essence of the primary rainbow, Alexander's band, and the secondary rainbow in succession for a given photon count P .

Conclusion: The model I've drawn is $x=720$ in $f(x)=x\sin(\pi/x) < \pi < x\tan(\pi/x)$ and offers a representation of the formation of primary and secondary rainbows in the context of the mathematical constant Pi. It paves the way for viewing natural wonders through a mathematical lens, uniting the ethereal beauty of rainbows with the elegance of mathematical constants.

In Simple Terms:

Pi in the Sky: A Mathematical Dive into the Magic of Rainbows

Introduction: Rainbows have always enchanted us with their sudden burst of color against the sky. Did you know that the mesmerizing arcs of a rainbow can be connected to a unique number

we all learned in school: Pi? This exploration attempts to unravel this link in the simplest of terms.

The Art of the Rainbow:

Let's start by understanding the rainbow itself. When the sun shines on droplets of moisture in the atmosphere, a rainbow can appear. A primary rainbow, the brightest and most vivid one, emerges due to light taking a single reflection inside water droplets. Above it, you might sometimes see a secondary, fainter rainbow, formed by light reflecting twice inside the droplets. The dark space in between? That's known as Alexander's band.

The Play of Light:

The richness and position of the rainbow's color bands depend on the number of sunlight particles, or photons, interacting with the droplets. Think of these particles as little actors. More actors can mean a more vibrant performance, or in the case of our rainbow, brighter and more pronounced colors.

Connecting to Pi:

Now, let's bring Pi into the picture. You might remember Pi as approximately 3.14 from math class, associated with circles. Rainbows, with their circular arcs, have an inherent link to circles and thus to Pi.

When we use the number of sunlight particles (photons) as an input into a special equation involving Pi, we get an outline resembling the primary rainbow. Use another, and you sketch the secondary rainbow. The space in between? Yep, Alexander's band.

In Simple Words: Imagine being an artist. Instead of paint, you have a number, Pi, and the number of sunlight particles. Using these, you can mathematically paint the picture of a double rainbow on the canvas of the sky.

Conclusion: Rainbows, as ethereal as they seem, hold a mathematical essence within them. By connecting the dots between the circular beauty of rainbows and the unique value of Pi, we uncover a delightful intersection of nature and numbers, showing once again that math is everywhere, even in the sky's most magical moments.